

Cardamom Sales Analysis Using Machine Learning and Power BI

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Abstract — A commodity's sales analysis is critical in crop production planning. The purpose of this project is to forecast and analyze Cardamom sales over time using the K-Neighbors Regression model.

Cardamom sales data in the Indian market were analysed and predicted using K-Neighbors Regression model in Power BI. Sales are appraised based on the amount of cardamom sold in the earlier auctions, and then the sales for next five years is determined. Forecast analytics in Power BI is used to predict sales using the K-Neighbors Regression model.

Keywords— *K-Neighbors Regression, Power BI, Machine learning.*

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the Cardamom (Licensing and Marketing) Rules 1987, cardamom producers can only sell cardamom through a licenced auctioneer/dealer; despite being India's largest foreign exchange earner, cardamom is not a free traded commodity. To predict and examine sales volume, machine learning algorithms such as K-Neighbors Regression are used. Because excellent sales are the lifeblood of any business. The main parameter used is the quantity sold.

Business intelligence has evolved into a critical solution for data mining, turning data from information to information, and assisting in decision-making. Designing a sales dashboard in Power BI using the K-Neighbors Regression model reflects sales performance and will investigate how a dataset may empower company and develop a report based on sales data.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Monika Raje et. al[1] The Power BI Marketing Dashboard has been updated with advertising data. Using multiple linear regression in Python, we have projected the expected sales through investment inputs of different marketing channels and visualised that in the Power BI Interactive Dashboard. This sales dashboard satisfies the needs of the sales department on the basis of the findings of the evaluation, analysis, and projection. Users may readily understand the sales performance by viewing the sales dashboard.

Ritesh Choudhary et. al[2] The goal of this paper is to analyze a big superstore's sales and predict their future sales in order to help them increase their profits and make their brand even better and competitive according to market trends while also generating customer satisfaction. The Linear

Regression Algorithm, a well-known algorithm in the field of Machine Learning, is used to predict sales.

Chejarla Venkata Narayana et. al[3] Every organisation knows the need of making sound and difficult decisions. This study focuses on one of the retail businesses that deals with used automobile sales. The main goal is to create a model that can anticipate the selling price of used cars based on important parameters. To achieve the purpose, machine learning techniques such as Random Forest Regression are used.

Shilpi Kulshrestha et. al[4] Forecast of Business expansion is a critical concern for the E-Commerce market's continued existence. Authorizing traditional procedures and analysis methods does not ensure the rate of accuracy of sales forecasting. We employ the ML algorithm to create more exact predictions and analysis. We will use a machine learning system to anticipate future earnings as well as analyse the most popular commodities and their frequency of purchase per quarter. Then, convey the results of the analysis and predictions of client buying patterns to the company organisation.

Weizhi Liao et. al[5] An auto Parts sales prediction approach based on Machine Learning for minimal data and a long replacement cycle is presented to estimate auto parts sales in auto component companies. The machine learning predictive model is mostly utilised for car parts with a long replacement cycle and limited data. We demonstrated through experiments that our machine learning-based model prediction method can accurately forecast car part sales with limited data and a long replacement interval.

III. BUILD MODEL

The purpose of this paper is to use K-Neighbors Regression model to predict the quantity of cardamom sold in future using the given dataset. The dataset is divided into two training and testing data sets. The result from this model can be used to analyze and predict the sales data using Power BI.

Data plays an important role in cardamom sales prediction and analysis. The required dataset is collected from Kaggle and the data from different auctions are gathered. The process consists of training phase and testing phase.

A. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsRegressor
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
```

```
df = pd.read_csv('Mainsheet1.csv')
```

B. Prepare the data set

```
df_trans=pd.get_dummies(df)
X = df_trans.drop(['QtySold'],axis=1)
y=df_trans['QtySold']
features = X.columns
```

```
s = StandardScaler()
X = s.fit_transform(X)
```

```
X_train,X_test,y_train,y_test = train_test_split(X,y)
```

C. Predict the K-Neighbours Regressor Model Performance

```
knn = KNeighborsRegressor(n_neighbors=9)
knn.fit(X_train,y_train)
```

```
KNeighborsRegressor(n_neighbors=9)
```

```
y_pred = knn.predict(X_test)
```

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Data acquisition –

Load the dataset into Power BI and use the KNN regressor model to predict and analyze cardamom sales in India.

B. Data cleaning and transformation –

Before modelling, utilize 'transform data' in Power BI to transform and clean the data.

C. Data modelling -

Perform python scripting in Power BI using the KNN Regressor model to predict the cardamom sales in future.

```
Script
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.neighbors import KNeighborsRegressor
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
knn=KNeighborsRegressor()
X = dataset.drop(['QtySold'],axis=1)
X = pd.get_dummies(X)
y=dataset['QtySold']
features = X.columns
s = StandardScaler()
X = s.fit_transform(X)
X_train,X_test,y_train,y_test = train_test_split(X,y)
knn.fit(X_train,y_train)
dataset['prediction'] = knn.predict(X)
```

Figure 1. Screenshot of KNN Regressor model in python script.

V. RESULT

The outcome demonstrates that, K-Neighbors Regression model forecasts the cardamom sales using Power BI for next 5 years.

Figure 2. Power BI screenshot of Cardamom sales analysis.

VI.CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

The results proved that the most conservative parameter 'QtySold' has been chosen for prediction. Thus, the K-Neighbors Regression model was shown to be the most relevant model for forecasting cardamom sales in the Indian market. This model is used in Power BI to analyze and predict cardamom sales in the Indian market during the period under consideration. The dataset can be extended and can use any other learning algorithms or tools to predict and analyze the sales of cardamom.

VII. REFERENCES

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